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CASTIEL 2

**CASTIEL 2 – Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level
Phase 2**

Project Number: 101102047

**D5.1
Initial Dissemination and Communication
Plan**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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Author(s):	Guntram Berti	SCAPOS
	Dennis Hoppe	USTUTT
	Miriam Koch	USTUTT
Approved by	Project Management Team	27.04.2020
Reviewer	Martina Blazkova	BSC
Reviewer	Laura Morselli	CINECA
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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CD	Corporate Design
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Development
CoE	Centre of Excellence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
Hx	Halfyear x
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analytics
ISC	International Supercomputing (trade fair)
IP	Intellectual Property
ISV	Independent Software Vendors
JU	Joint Undertaking
NCC	National Competence Centre
PMT	Project Management Team
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The document “D5.1 Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan” is the first deliverable of CASTIEL 2’s Work Package 5 (WP5): Awareness, Impact and Outreach. This document forms the basis for all communication and dissemination activities from and related to CASTIEL2. It will be updated and reported on in D5.3, D5.5 and D5.7 (M12, M24 and M36).

Work Package 5 aims to plan and implement communication and dissemination measures that are related to and support the achievement of the CASTIEL 2 project’s objectives, as well as assisting the National Competence Centres (NCCs) of the EuroCC 2 project and Centres of Excellence (CoEs) with their communication efforts.

In this deliverable 5.1, first the objectives of Work Package 5 are analysed with regard to CASTIEL 2’s target audiences and tailored messages. Second, the document describes which channels and communication tools will be used in order to achieve the goals related to these target groups. For completeness, an overview about the tasks related to the information system C2ISS and the continuous integration of Codes are also given. Finally, the monitoring and measurement of progress and success factors will be outlined in this deliverable.

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1. Introduction

CASTIEL 2 will continue the mission of the CASTIEL H2020 project to coordinate and support the National Competence Centres of EuroCC 2 and in addition will now coordinate and support the Centres of Excellence in HPC. The activities of CASTIEL 2 will facilitate the NCC and CoE activities at the European level, and foster collaborations between NCCs and CoEs (and amongst each other) to achieve maximum impact to their user communities and the European HPC landscape. As strategic communication and dissemination have repeatedly been proven crucial for the success of the undertaking, this work package (WP) will directly contribute to the achievements of the project.

As the new phase provides support to both NCCs and CoEs, the following aspects need to be considered: the NCCs already have a common EuroCC brand; the CoEs already have strong individual brands and the prior Coordination and Support Action (CSA) FocusCoE supported the development of the general HPC CoE brand and representation through the hpccoe.eu website. The EuroCC brand will be continued and another “Competence and Excellence Network” brand will be created to include all entities. A separate CASTIEL brand will not be developed, since it is not relevant to the target groups. Another focus of this WP is on enabling the individual champions (communication representatives) of the Centres to professionally communicate their brands by supporting with communication material, fostering the exchange between the communication teams and helping with implementing their brands.

Furthermore, this WP will cover the information sharing system C2ISS, that is to be developed by CASTIEL 2. The system will be a platform to centrally store information about NCCs and CoEs and provide them to other websites with APIs as well.

This deliverable will provide information about the objectives, target groups and evaluation mechanisms used in Work Package 5. This document provides strategic measures and tools, an overview of the NCC and CoE communication as well as plans for the C2ISS and the Continuous Integration platform and will close with an outlook onto the implementation of the strategy.

2. Dissemination strategy

As the dissemination strategy is directly influencing the success of the projects through visibility, it has to be based on a targeted approach with the respective objectives and target audiences.

2.1 Dissemination objectives

1) Continue and increase awareness about the European NCC and HPC in Europe brands:

Industry, academia and other stakeholders should be aware of the NCCs as a first contact point to the “world of HPC” in their respective countries. Furthermore, NCCs should be associated with solution finding, HPC, HPDA and AI competences, skills and European interconnection. The CoEs under the HPC in Europe brand should be considered as excellence hubs in specific domains and associated with spearheading algorithm development as well as fundamentally connected to the EuroHPC landscape.

2) Create and promote the Competence and Excellence Network Brand

The stakeholders should be able to get a quick and easy overview about the NCCs and CoEs network and identify if an entity is part of it or not. To enable this in the rather complicated project ecosystem, an umbrella brand for the Competence and Excellence Network will be created.

3) Support the CoEs and NCCs communication efforts:

To assist the CoEs and NCCs in their communication efforts, this working group will expand the existing material database. This will strongly support the CoEs and NCCs, since they can use templates or ready-made material instead of or in addition to producing their own. Additionally, the project channels will be used to amplify content from the Centres.

2.2 Target groups

The target groups are as diverse as the participating countries. The following table will give an overview of the types of target groups and their communication needs towards the EuroCC, HPCCoE and Competence and Excellence Network brands.

Target Group	Communication needs	Tailored Messages	Channels
European Commission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on project status • Information on how the European interests are implemented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CASTIEL 2 shows the EU through dissemination the current project status 	Social Media, Websites, Events, (indirectly: Media Relations/Publications)
European HPC Ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on project status • Information for possible collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CASTIEL 2 shows the EU through dissemination the current project status • The NCCs and CoEs are strong partners for collaboration in the European HPC environment • CASTIEL 2 supports the NCCs and CoEs in connecting with other initiatives • CASTIEL 2 supports the aims of the European HPC strategy 	Social Media, Website, Events, Media Relations/Publications
Industrial End Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the project itself • Information on how and why they could use HPC services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NCCs and CoEs are competent contact points for industrial applications 	Social Media, Website, Events, Media Relations, White papers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and fast overview about HPC competences • Access to success stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NCCs and CoEs have experience with industrial applications • The NCCs and CoEs help enterprises to increase their competitiveness 	
Academic End Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the project itself • Information on how and why they could use HPC services • Easy and fast overview about HPC competences • Access to success stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NCCs and CoEs are competent contact points for academic applications • HPC is an important driver for academic progress 	Social Media, Website, Publications, Media Relations
Political Decision Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the project itself • Information on how and why they could use HPC services • Easy and fast overview about HPC competences • Access to success stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NCCs and CoEs are competent contact points for HPC applications • HPC is an important tool to solve societal and political challenges 	Social Media, Website, Publications, Media Relations
Public Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the project itself • Information on how and why they could use HPC services • Easy and fast overview about HPC competences • Access to success stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NCCs and CoEs are competent contact points for HPC applications • HPC is an important tool to solve societal and political challenges 	Social Media, Website, Publications, Media Relations
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the project itself • Updates on project status • Answer to the question: What are we 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HPC is an important area with societal impact that should be strengthened by the EU 	Social Media, Website, Media Relations

	financing with our taxes? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about HPC competences / activities Information about regional and European impact of HPC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HPC can create jobs and reputation for the participating countries The EU is competitive in the field of HPC 	
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Table 1: Strategic dissemination overview of the target groups

2.3 The Corporate Designs

The EuroCC brand was developed in phase 1 of the project; the Brand Handbook is attached in the Annex. To ensure brand continuity, the EuroCC channels will continue to use the light version of the old logo, see Figures 1. For project specific communication, the new one (Figures 1) will be used. The colour schemes will stay the same, see Figure 3.

Figures 1 and 2: The old and new EuroCC Logo.

#ffffff	#8f8f8f	##b8860b
R: 255 G: 255 B: 255	R: 143 G: 143 B: 143	R: 184 G: 134 B: 11

Figure 3: Color Scheme of the EuroCC Brand

The HPC CoE Brand was developed by the discontinued FocusCoE project. The umbrella brand will be kept and the logo (Figures 4) will be expanded with a corporate identity.

Figure 4: The HPC CoE Logo.

For the Competence and Excellence Network, the brand is still to be created together with the CoEs and NCCs, a first draft of the logo can be found in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Logo Draft for the Competence and Excellence Network

3. Dissemination measures and tools

3.1 Internal Communications

To achieve a valid information flow within the project, this WP planned a series of mechanisms: this will include separate channels, like project internal mailing lists as well as channels that are “shared” with the external communication such as social media, or the EuroCC ACCESS website.

Internal newsletter

A weekly newsletter is sent out by the Project Management Team (PMT) which includes general information, deadlines and interesting or upcoming events. It is addressed to all members of the EuroCC 2 project. This will ensure that those collaborating in EuroCC 2 are informed about the current overall project status.

Specific channels for champions

To foster communication between and to the respective champions, CASTIEL 2 provides dedicated tools (e.g. mailing lists, Slack channel). This ensures that the champions have room for subject-specific discussions and questions.

3.2 Events and workshops

Events will be a vital part of the CASTIEL 2 project's communication and dissemination activities. The project will select the most relevant conferences and exhibitions for participation and booth presence; it will also participate in related European Commission (EC) and EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) events, and organise own conferences and workshops especially for and with the NCCs and CoEs. All events CASTIEL 2 participates in or organises will regularly be promoted via the EuroCC ACCESS website, the social media channels and other relevant communication channels. This shall give the community an overview over recent events. CASTIEL 2 will be involved in the following event types:

Project conferences

There will be three conferences in total with all members and participants from EuroCC 2, CASTIEL2 and the CoEs; one of those conferences was already hosted in February 2023 (the project Kick-Off). In person events have been proven extremely beneficial for the collaboration between the Centres, since it is the opportunity to connect beyond working groups and discuss diverse project facets. It also fosters the information flow from CASTIEL 2 to the CoEs and NCCs, which is crucial for the success of the project.

(External) Conferences and other events

In addition to events organised by CASTIEL 2, the project will also interact with its stakeholders and other EU initiatives in larger events, such as ICT, ISC or EuroHPC Summit. The following table includes potential events that CASTIEL 2 could participate in. In addition to the HPC specific events, the plan for the second phase is to visit sector specific events to establish the projects also outside of the HPC ecosystem. In some cases, the participation might entail a booth, in some participation in the conference programme.

Event	Target Audience	Organiser
HPC Events		
Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	EU, Partners, Academia	European Commission
International Supercomputing Conference (ISC)	Scientific conference and exhibition	ISC Group
Supercomputing conference	Partners, academia, industry	Supercomputing
EuroHPC Summit	Industry, academia	ETP4HPC and EuroHPC
Sectorial Events (examples, to be further refined with WP4)		

BDVA Conference	Industry, academia	BDVA
Control	Industry	
Exopharm	Industry	
BIO-Europe	Industry	

Table 2: Potential events

3.3 Publications and white papers

To disseminate the project's progress and successful achievements, press releases, white papers and in some cases scientific publications have been proven to be valuable tools. While press releases for the European scale will be produced by this work package and distributed through press lists, whitepapers will be sourced from the NCCs. Scientific publications will be organised through a CASTIEL 2 – NCC/CoE consortium according to the opportunity arises (e.g. call for special issues).

3.4 Print material

WP5 will update and further develop the existing portfolio of print material templates for the NCCs and add material for the CoEs, such as flyers, posters or roll ups, that are available and adaptable for all NCCs. This is important for the competence and excellence Centres to be able to quickly and easily present the projects and their work. The material will be created in accordance with the corporate design.

3.5 Website

The EuroCC ACCESS and hpccoe portals will be further developed and transformed into the C2ISS. For more, see Web Portals & the C2ISS.

3.6 Social media

WP5 will continue the EuroCC Social Media channels (see Figure 6) accounts and take over and update the FocusCoE accounts (See Figure 6) towards the HPC CoE Brand established in the website, in order to continue building the community and increase the awareness for the projects. The CASTIEL channels will be left online, but not further maintained, since the CASTIEL brand should not be visible.

Figures 6 and 7: EuroCC and FocusCoE Twitter Profiles.

While Twitter mainly targets the EU audience, the partners/consortium, academic stakeholders, the general public, and the interaction with other projects, LinkedIn should mainly reach the industrial target audience. Furthermore, the use of Twitter is under reconsideration due to the recent changes of the platform. Mastodon is considered as an alternative and will be tested and evaluated.

Following CASTIEL 2's overall communication strategy in the beginning, the social media accounts have mainly been used following three different approaches:

- 1) **An event-driven communication**, which means that events, such as the signature of the Grant Agreement, the project kick-off, the initial website launch, and further news were communicated via the social media followers.
- 2) **An informative communication** approach, introducing the project partners, the objectives and first steps of the consortium, etc.
- 3) **Replication of content** from either NCCs' or CoEs' own social channels or news and success stories from the websites, to gain additional reach and cross-promote.

3.7 Media relations

CASTIEL 2 will continue to collaborate with the NCCs (through the communication & dissemination champions) and thus identify relevant recurring topics, like NCCs' news, and get selected interview partners to speak about specific topics to the press; in the best case resulting in feature articles and special issues. A selected list of relevant media in English can be found in Table 3.

Magazine	Area
HPCwire	HPC news
InsideHPC	HPC news
Scientific Computing World	HPC news

Horizon Magazine	EU-funded research
Cordis	EU-funded research
Science Node	Applied HPC
Research & Development	Applied Science

Table 3: List of relevant media.

4. Performance evaluation (KPIs)

To evaluate the success of CASTIEL 2's communication and dissemination efforts, a number of KPIs and respective targets are listed in the Description of Action of the projects Grant Agreement (GA) (see Table 4). The values are based on the consortium's experiences from phase 1. These will be regularly monitored and reported, which helps to keep track of the project's current progress and take measures to improve its activities accordingly.

Tool	KPI	Target
Publications	Press Releases	2
	Success Story Booklets	2
Events	CASTIEL/Network of NCC/CoEs presentations at conferences/events	20
	Significant presence at events (e.g. booths)	5
	Number of own events (public)	3
Social Media	Number of Twitter postings, Followers	Daily postings, 300 Followers p.a.
	Number of LinkedIn Postings, Followers	Weekly Postings, 250 Followers p.a.
Reference in external media channels (Online & Offline)	Press Clippings	40
Websites	Number of visits	10,000 unique p.a.

Table 4: Overview of KPIs and Targets.

5. NCC Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The goal is to support the NCC communication in a well-rounded way. This includes enabling the transfer of knowledge and material between the NCCs through file sharing systems and meetings. Furthermore, the existing material pool will be expanded to give easily accessible material and on-boarding handbooks to the communication champions. Continuous feedback loops will be implemented to get the inputs from the NCCs to improve EuroCC brand in the best way possible.

6. CoEs Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Task 5.3 will build on previous activities carried out in FocusCoE and the HPC CoE brand created during that time, to specifically support CoE visibility and dissemination. One focus will be on activities with a high added value compared to individual CoE activities.

Besides collection & compilation of CoE use cases and success stories, the creation of articles highlighting the collective role of CoEs in addressing major societal challenges will be another focus, continuing the series of such pieces started in FocusCoE (with articles on climate change modelling and research on fighting the COVID-19 pandemic). This task also plans to issue an update of the “CoE impact brochure” published in March 2022, presenting each CoE on a single page accessible to the interested public.

Further activities will focus on presenting CoEs and their codes in a recognisable format, for instance in a “code of the month” series (jointly with WP4 and WP2, presenting a code from different angles and different media, like webinars, short teasers on social media, blog entries, interviews etc.).

Another thread of activity will work – in close interaction with the CoEs – on carrying out support activities and communication-related competence building for CoE dissemination activities, in particular for reaching out to a wider audience.

7. Web Portals & the C2ISS

In a first analysis of the portal system, it was shown that the information about the NCCs and CoEs, their services, trainings and codes as well as success stories and best practices is distributed among different platforms. This leads to an unclear user guidance when it comes to finding information for the different target groups. For this, the C2ISS as a central database will be implemented. The C2ISS will be embedded in a platform that will serve as a central point of contact for the Competence and Excellence Network. More information on this will be given in D5.2 - Design strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal.

8. Continuous Integration Platform

For the sake of completeness, since this will be a topic for communication and the work is located in this WP, a short outlook on the continuous integration platform is given, which is subject to change:

CASTIEL2 has established a monthly status call with stakeholders from all CoE and EuroHPC hosting sites to discuss the implementation and practical usage of a continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) platform for EuroHPC systems. The motivation is to ease the deployment of CoE codes onto the EuroHPC supercomputers infrastructure. Doing so also increases the overall code quality due to an automated quality check and testing mechanism.

To date, CASTIEL2 discussed the Special Access Scheme that offers long-term access to compute resources for CoE members on EuroHPC HPC systems; for which the project gathered relevant information from CoEs through a spreadsheet. Furthermore, CASTIEL2 sent questionnaires to CoEs and EuroHPC hosting sites to collect information about chances and technical limitations when deploying onto EuroHPC HPC systems. In this context, an initial technical roadmap foresees easing deployment through containerising CoE codes. However, although most EuroHPC hosting sites support container technologies, adopting containerisation is little widespread. Still, containerisation is up for discussion.

From a technical point of view, CoEs and EuroHPC hosting sites are looking into Jacamar CI, a continuous integration platform based on GitLab, which already comes with customised extensions to deploy applications on HPC. The overall objective is to implement a CI/CD platform on top of what already exists on a CoE level while keeping additional components as loosely coupled as possible. That is why the choice falls onto Jacamar CI, where agents could be deployed independently at each EuroHPC hosting site to fetch new software artefacts for compilation, testing, and deployment from remote and shared code repositories.

Technical discussions will continue between CoEs and EuroHPC hosting sites to agree upon a feasible and practicable solution in H1 2023 so that the set-up and configuration can be realised in H2 2023 to deploy the first CoE application through a CI/CD platform onto EuroHPC HPC systems.

9. Next Steps

This document will be updated in the deliverables D5.3, D5.5 and D5.7. In the next months, the main efforts of WP5 will be to implement the dissemination plan drafted in this document and to continue the development of the C2ISS and its framework platform. The upcoming deliverables are shown in Table 5

Number	Title	Due	Status
D5.1	Initial Dissemination and Communication Plan	M4	Submitted
D5.2	Design strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M9	To be submitted
D5.3	First report on awareness, impact and outreach	M12	To be submitted

D5.4	Explanatory report on initial launch of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M15	To be submitted
D5.5	Second report on awareness, impact and outreach	M24	To be submitted
D5.6	Explanatory report in the final version of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC Access Portal	M30	To be submitted
D5.7	Final report on awareness, impact and outreach	M36	To be submitted
D5.8	CI/CD Platform	M12	To be submitted
D5.9	First Update of the CI/CD Platform	M24	To be submitted
D5.10	Second Update of the CI/CD Platform	M36	To be submitted

Table 5: Overview CASTIEL WP5 Deliverables.

In WP5, CASTIEL 2 reached the first milestone with the project kick off, which was supported by initial plans and a presentation of WP5. The second milestone was achieved through the active participation in the 1st Global Workshop. Milestone (MS) 3 will be reached in month four, with the launch of the EuroCC ACCESS. The fourth and last relevant MS4 for WP5 will be achieved with the preparation of and active attendance at the Intermediate Global Workshop.

Number	Title	Due	Status
MS3	Design Strategy for the evolved EuroCC Access portal and the C2ISS are ready	M9	Open
MS5	Evolved EuroCC Access portal is launched	M15	Open
MS7	Final implementation of the evolved EuroCC Access portal and the C2ISS	M30	Open

Table 6: Overview CASTIEL WP5 Milestones.

10. Conclusion

The communication strategy, channels, and tactics in this deliverable will be continuously verified and adapted when necessary throughout the entire project. There is a series of mechanisms in place that regularly control the quality, success and reach of the communication measures. This WP will be the central contact point for all NCCs and CoEs and will foster interaction between the participants. All this should contribute to a recognisable brand landscape, while giving autonomy to the individual NCCs and CoEs.

Furthermore, the C2ISS will substantially contribute to the project's success by providing a central point of information for stakeholders as well as a central source of information regarding HPC competences, services and trainings.